

Jörmungandr's Elemental Diets: The World Snake — An Immersive Educational Videogame for Exploring the Periodic Table of Elements with Real-World Contexts and Examples

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Abstract

This work introduces an immersive educational video game designed to facilitate the exploration and understanding of the periodic table of elements within real-world contexts and examples. The periodic table serves as a foundational tool in chemistry education, enabling students to comprehend the properties and behaviors of chemical elements. While traditional memorization techniques have been utilized for learning the periodic table, the potential of serious games as educational aids remains largely untapped. Drawing inspiration from the famous Snake game, where the player maneuvers the end of a growing line, the snake, which gets longer with each piece of food eaten, “Jörmungandr's Elemental Diets: The World Snake” (JED), represents a significant evolution in learning experiences. Instead of consuming apples or eggs, the snake in JED consumes specific elements of the periodic table of elements —grouped in different diets that can be selected at the beginning of the game — inspired to didactic and actual real-world contexts. JED offers an engaging and stimulating environment where players can select different categories of elements to consume, akin to the concept of flashcards, challenging them to classify elements into specific groups quickly and accurately. This dynamic gameplay —the element of urgency and required quick thinking— not only reinforces knowledge of element classification, but also enhances cognitive skills such as pattern recognition and decision-making under pressure. At the end of each game level, players receive insights related to the chosen diet, providing a deeper understanding of the topic. Moreover, is easily modifiable and expandable, offering a valuable opportunity for instructors and students to delve into programming while nurturing their passion for chemistry, with the JED code readily available as open source Python package at a public GitHub repository.

Graphical abstract

Introduction

The periodic table of elements stands as a fundamental pillar in chemistry education, serving as a roadmap for understanding the intricate properties and behaviors of chemical elements. (1) However, traditional methods of teaching often rely on rote memorization techniques, leading to a disconnect between students and the underlying concepts of the periodic table. (2) The association between elements and their group and period numbers, along with other crucial factual information, can be challenging to reason and cumbersome to commit to memory. While mnemonic devices have been employed to aid in this endeavor, they often fall short in providing a comprehensive understanding and may overlook significant aspects such as group numbers. (3)

Recognizing the need for innovative approaches to supplement or reinvent traditional teaching methods, the concept of serious games emerges as a promising avenue. (4–9) Serious games, designed with an educational purpose in mind, offer an engaging and interactive platform for learning, steering away from the monotony of memorization towards a more dynamic and immersive experience. Inspired by the iconic Snake game, this endeavor introduces "Jörmungandr's Elemental Diets: The World Snake" (JED), a groundbreaking educational video game poised to revolutionize the exploration of the periodic table during relaxing times.

In the spirit of the Snake game, (10) where the player guides a growing line (the snake) to consume objects, JED adopts a similar premise with a unique twist — instead of traditional game items, players navigate the snake to consume specific elements of the periodic table, arranged in distinct diets inspired by actual real-world issues, such as critical raw materials, (11) smartphone, (12) fusion power plan, (13) radioactivity (14), coupled with more conventional ensembles, such as p-block (15), curious ensembles like elements dedicated

to scientists, (16) ensembles linked to biology or geology, (17) and many others possible ensembles that can be easily implemented into the code. These diets, representing different categories of elements, challenge players to swiftly classify elements into specific groups, akin to the concept of flashcards, (18,19) thereby reinforcing element classification while honing cognitive skills such as pattern recognition and decision-making. Moreover, JED transcends conventional gaming experiences by offering players valuable insights related to the chosen diet at the conclusion of each game section, fostering a deeper understanding of the periodic table and its relevance in real-world scenarios. JED is written in Python (20), but its usage does not require any programming skills beyond what is required to install the software; JED was designed to primarily be a video game. Video games as educational tools can reach larger audiences and have yielded improved learning outcomes in the sciences. As such, the intention is that JED may be easily used by anyone to unlock the mysteries of the periodic table in an engaging and transformative manner. The modifiability and expansibility of JED further elevate its educational potential, providing instructors and students with a unique opportunity to delve into programming while nurturing their passion for chemistry. For this scope the JED's code was deposited as a free and open source Python package at the GitHub repository (21). The wide expansion potentialities of this game, not only in terms of group of elements and insights given at the end of each game, but also in terms of game experience since it can be developed as online multiplayer game where players challenge each other in different Jörmungandr's elemental diets in a format similar to the Kahoot's one. (22,23)

Finally, it is worth to note the framework where the idea of JED was born: the project entitled "Change the Game: Playing to Prepare for the Challenges of a Sustainable Society", (24) which aimed in raising the interest towards sustainability through the design and testing of serious games. (25–29)

Game contest

The game is set within Norse mythology, featuring Jörmungandr, the world serpent that encircles the Earth (Midgard) by biting its own tail until its confrontation with Thor during Ragnarök, the world's final battle. (30) This mythical backdrop not only creates an engaging atmosphere but also establishes a connection with an element from the periodic table, Thorium (Th). This link, as detailed in the "*Rules and Gameplay*" section, allows for the departure from conventional rules observed in traditional snake games, injecting a sense of fun and originality that distinguishes the game from its counterparts.

Game Design

JED takes inspiration from the famous Snake game, in which the player controls a snake that grows as it eats food. However, instead of eating apples or eggs as in the traditional game, the snake Jörmungandr in JED eats specific elements from the periodic table, grouped into different "diets" that can be selected at the beginning of the game.

Rules and Gameplay

To control the snake in JED, players can use arrow keys or the letters A, D, S, W (mainly indicated for left-handed players). These directional controls enable players to navigate the snake throughout the game environment, directing it to consume the elements supposedly belonging to the selected diet displayed in the main window below the sentence "Jörmungandr is hungry of" (see Fig. 1). As the snake consumes an element, it grows longer, adding to the challenge of maneuvering without colliding with the game boundaries or the snake's own body. The player's score is reported in the main window following the sentence "Just eaten:" (see Fig. 1). A unique feature of JED is that the score increases only if the consumed element belongs to the selected diet; otherwise, it decreases. The scoring mechanism is designed, according to the equations Eq. 1 and Eq. 2, to balance scores, ensuring that random selection of elements to eat does not provide an advantage. When a player believes an element does not belong to the diet, they can press the space bar to discard it. Similarly, the score adjusts using the same formulas (Eq. 1 and Eq. 2) to prevent any inadvertent advantage.

$$S_+ = \frac{118}{118 - N} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$S_- = \frac{118}{N} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

Where, S_+ and S_- are the positive and negative calculated score, respectively, N is the number of elements presented in the selected diet and 118 corresponds to the total number of known elements.

After discarding an element, a new one is randomly chosen from the periodic table and appears in a random position on the game field. These rules apply to all elements except Th, which leads to the game over, as warned in the main window: "It cannot eat Thor!" (see Fig. 1). This intuitive control scheme offers players a straightforward yet engaging means to interact with the game and delve into the periodic table concepts within the immersive gameplay experience.

Figure 1. JED main window displaying the snake (depicted as segmented green blocks) and the food (represented, in this case, by the Th element). In the header above the game field, the selected diet and current score are highlighted by the red rectangles and pointed to by arrows linked to the corresponding labels. Additionally, the message 'It cannot eat Thor!' warns players that consuming the Thor element leads to the end of the game.

Jörmungandr's Elemental Diets

In JED, the extensive selection of 32 implemented diets provides users with an educational and engaging experience that spans various scientific disciplines and beyond (see Fig. 2). Each diet has been selected to reflect important aspects of elemental properties and classifications, resulting in a diverse array of themes. For instance, the "elements of life" diet guides players through the fundamental building blocks of matter, elucidated by Isaac Asimov, underscoring the significance of elements in biology and the chemistry of life. (17) Similarly, the "elements of DNA" diet delves into the genetic fundamentals of life. (31) These diets not only promote understanding of materials science but also have significant implications in other scientific disciplines such as biology and medicine.

Additionally, many diets offer interesting connections with history, geography, and narrative, further enriching the gaming experience. (16) For example, the "elements dedicated to scientists" diet celebrates historical figures who contributed to the discovery and understanding of chemical elements, integrating elements of the history of science into the game's storyline. Similarly, the "elements with names of Latin or Greek derivation" diet sets the stage for an exploration of the linguistic and cultural origins of element nomenclature, providing historical and linguistic context to scientific breakthroughs. These multidisciplinary connections enhance the gaming experience, stimulating curiosity and understanding of the interconnections between science, history, and culture.

Furthermore, some diets have political and economic implications, such as the "critical raw elements" diet, (11,32) which explores the global dependency on rare elements and their impact on key industries like technology (e.g. smartphones (12)) and energy. These diets raise important questions about supply security, sustainability, and equity in resource access, offering users an opportunity to explore the socio-economic implications of natural resources and modern technology such as the fusion the fusion power plan. (13)

Additionally, JED incorporates groups linked to the periodicity of the periodic table. (33) However, the game's flexibility allows for the seamless addition of further diets, enabling the creative connection of chemical elements to natural sciences, history, geography, narrative, and political and economic issues, thereby enhancing understanding and knowledge of the elements comprehensively.

Figure 2. Screenshot of the diet selection window in JED, displaying the diverse range of 32 implemented diets available for selection. Users can choose from this comprehensive list, with each diet focusing on different aspects of elemental properties and classifications, as outlined in the code snippet. Upon selection, the chosen diet determines the elements that the snake must consume during gameplay to score points.

Game over: keep to stay hungry, stay periodic!

While playing JED can enhance one's ability to classify elements, the moment of game over offers an opportunity to impart a powerful message or profound insight into the selected diet's topic. Therefore, upon reaching the game over screen, a message closely related to the chosen diet is displayed (see Fig. 3). "Stay hungry, stay periodic" replaces the typical "GAME OVER," echoing Steve Jobs' famous and inspiring quote, "Stay hungry, stay foolish." This serves as a positive motto, encouraging players to maintain their curiosity and

commitment to periodic exploration even in the face of complexity.

Fig. 3 Screenshot of the game over window ("stay hungry, stay periodic" window). In this example the message correlated to the "element of life" diet is printed.

As a Python Package

Turning JED into a Python package allows users to delve deeper into its functionalities and customize potentials or entire game levels according to their preferences. While utilizing JED as a Python package may necessitate some coding proficiency, modifying existing diets or creating new ones is a feasible task. With clear explanations provided for different parts of the code, both students and instructors can engage with the codebase and experiment with creating tailored gaming experiences.

Future Work

Further improvements to the game are currently being explored, including enhancements to code organization and documentation. One potential enhancement is the implementation of a feature to save player records, along with their names, in a text file. Additionally, a top-ten leaderboard could be implemented to showcase the highest scores achieved for each specific diet in a secondary window. Another proposed improvement is the addition of options to adjust the speed of the snake within the main menu, offering players the choice of different difficulty levels. Furthermore, there is potential to introduce weighted scoring based on specific parameters, such as the abundance of each element in a given context (e.g., smartphone components or elements found in the Earth's crust or atmosphere). The scoring system could also be adjusted to consider decay rates or other physical and chemical properties of elements. Exploring the possibility of creating a comprehensive figure of merit that incorporates multiple parameters is also on the agenda. There are numerous creative avenues to explore for enhancing the insights provided at the end of the game. One idea is to generate multiple sentences for each diet and randomly select one to display, increasing player curiosity. Alternatively, sentences could be displayed based on the player's mistakes, providing additional information about elements that negatively impact their score. In addition to these gameplay enhancements, graphical improvements could be considered, such as the addition of new visual elements to enhance the overall aesthetic appeal of the game. Additionally, considering the conversion of JED into a web-based student response game to provide instant feedback to students and instructors, while promoting active learning and student engagement, is being considered. This expansion could facilitate the integration of the game into classroom settings and support Formative Assessment Classroom Techniques (FACTs).(22,34)

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Notes

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Jörmungandr's Elemental Diets: The World Snake source code: <https://github.com/PietroGalizia/JED.git>

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